

SMART TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN FACILITY MANAGEMENT: A TOOL FOR EFFICIENCY AND SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides an overview of the integration of smart technology in facility management, offering insights and case studies for efficient facilities. Smart technologies are advanced systems, devices, and solutions that leverage connectivity, data, and intelligent processing to adapt to user needs and perform tasks more efficiently. Examples of Smart technologies are smartphones, smart home gadgets, voice-activated assistants and various Internet of Things devices. Smart technology often adapts to user preferences, providing personalized experiences, as evident in applications ranging from personalized recommendations on platforms to customized settings. They are designed to collect, analyse, and utilise data to make informed decisions or perform specific tasks, which aims to make daily activities more convenient, efficient and accessible. Facility management plays a critical role in ensuring seamless operations of diverse infrastructures. Smart technology has become an essential tool for facility management, offering a range of benefits that contribute to its improved efficiency, sustainability, and overall operational effectiveness. The integration of smart technologies in facility management, examining the benefits, challenges, and future prospects in reshaping facilities management with promises of further innovations and advancements of the society is discussed in this paper. No doubt the advent of smart technology introduces a new era characterized by data-driven decision-making that continues to shape our societies, economies, and individual lifestyles.

Keywords: Smart Technology, Integration, Facility Management, Efficiency, Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Smart technologies are advanced systems, devices, and solutions that leverage connectivity, sensors, and intelligent processing to adapt to user needs and perform tasks more efficiently and interactivity REF. These dynamic technologies are a combination of information and communication technologies (ICT) and sensing systems, used to create a variety of potential applications. They often use features like automation, data analysis, machine learning and artificial intelligence to enhance functionality. They are designed to collect, analyze, and utilize data to make informed decisions or perform specific tasks. Examples of Smart technologies include devices like smartphones, smart home gadgets, wearable fitness trackers, voice-activated assistants and various Internet of Things (IoT). Smart devices are often interconnected through the internet or other communication networks, allowing the exchange of information with the operation done collaboratively, thereby enabling Users to monitor and manage the devices from a distance.

The advent of smart technologies introduced a new era characterized by connectivity, automation, and data-driven decision-making which continues to shape our societies, economies, and individual lifestyles. It representing a significant evolution in the interaction and management of various aspects of lives. Smart technologies offer unprecedented opportunities to enhance facility management processes, and this opportunity has changed how facilities are managed, leading to increased efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability.

The International Facility Management Association (IFMA) defines Facility or facilities management (FM) as a profession dedicated to supporting people. It ensures the functionality, comfort, safety, sustainability and efficiency of the built environment - the buildings we live and work in and their surrounding infrastructure (IFMA, 2023). Also, as defined by the International Standard Organization (ISO) and adopted and adopted by IFMA, Facility Management is an organizational function which integrates people, place and process within the built environment with the purpose of improving the quality of life of people and the productivity of the core business (ISO, 2017).

Smart technologies aim to make daily activities more convenient, efficient, accessible and connected as evident in smart homes, wearable devices, and other technologies that seamlessly integrate into our routines and various aspects of daily life. The integration of smart technologies is reshaping facility management with promises of further innovations and advancements for the betterment of man and the society. This paper provides an overview of the integration of smart technology in facility management, offering insights and case studies for efficient facilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Some of the applications of these technologies include **Smartphones and Virtual Assistants Devices** that integrate various smart technologies for communication, navigation, and personal assistance; in **Smart Home Devices**, which make use of intelligent power scheduling algorithms (for decision making) and ICT (for control), in home features like lighting, security cameras, thermostats, etc. In the application of smart technologies in Healthcare (**Smart Health Devices**) through Health-Monitoring Devices, Health-Wearable Devices and Health-Tracking Apps which enable Users to monitor their health in real-time and provide valuable data for healthcare professionals. **Health-Monitoring Devices** allow the independence of Users in their comfortable home environment rather than in expensive and limited homes or hospitals (Bolchini, *et al.*, 2017). Monitoring of the Users environment conditions (such as temperature, humidity, airflow and smoke in the home); important physiological signs (such as blood pressure, body temperature, heart rate, and blood oxygen level), and activities can be achieved and communicated with remote healthcare professionals or facilities, thus allowing the tracking of the overall physiological condition of the Users from a distant facility (Capozzoli, *et al.*, 2018); (Faia, *et al.*, 2017). Some of these technologies also come as wearable devices (Fitness trackers, smartwatches, etc.) which collect and analyze data related to health of the User; and **Industrial IoT Devices** which serve as sensors and automation in manufacturing processes for predictive maintenance and increased efficiency.

Internet of Things (IoT) is explained as the network that connects through the internet and stipulates processes through information exchange and communications (Dahanayake and Sumanarathna, 2021). Mobile devices and technologies such as data management and cloud systems are significant components in IoT. The role of IoT applications has recently become relevant to sustainable development management as it has enabled the improvement of resource transmission of smart cities, removal of environmental pollutants and the development of waste management and transport controlling systems (Lee *et al.*, 2021). Evjen *et al.*, 2020 present the practical implementation of IoT applications in the field of FM.

SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN FACILITY MANAGEMENT

In recent years, facility management (FM) industries have been applying various emerging digital technologies to facilitate the design, construction and management of facilities. Facility management plays an important role in ensuring seamless operations of diverse infrastructures.

Smart technologies including IoT sensors for real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance utilizing machine learning algorithms, energy management systems, and integrated building management systems has become an essential tool for facility management, offering a range of benefits that contribute to improved efficiency, sustainability, and overall operational effectiveness. For a more strategic and effective facility management, Smart technologies helps in making data-driven decisions through the vast of data generated, leading to more informed and data-driven decision-making in various fields where systems within a facility can remotely be monitored and controlled, providing flexibility and the ability to respond promptly to issues or changing circumstances.

Though there is currently extensive literature on Facility Management, but only very few that integrates Smart Technologies in Facility Management. A holistic approach to facilities management (FM) in which the management of organization-wide systems and processes and, typically, service providers are centralized under a single outsourced, technology-focused platform is referred to as integrated facilities management (<https://www.enternest.com/>). Smart FM is defined as the integration of systems, processes, technologies and personnel to enhance the management of a facilities. It describes the use digital tools to optimise the management of facilities. For example, a smart building typically has smart integration in the form of a series of smart systems, smart components, smart devices, etc. Despite the fact that the use of ST in the FM has been increased significantly over the last decade, research on smart FM is limited (Huiying, 2023).

ADOPTION OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN FACILITY MANAGEMENT

The adoption of smart technologies is a global trend, and Nigeria has been making strides in incorporating these technologies in various sectors of the economy. Some cities are beginning to explore the **Smart City** initiatives to enhance city living by incorporating the technologies for intelligent energy management, waste management, data-driven urban planning and **Smart Traffic Management Solutions** (Traffic Management and Transportation Systems) through the use of smart traffic lights and real-time monitoring systems to address congestion and enhance transportation efficiency, all for improved public services.

In Agriculture, agricultural practices in Nigeria are now optimized as a result of the adoption of smart technologies in agriculture through the use of IoT devices for crop monitoring; data analytics for precision farming, and weather forecasting. In the **Banking and Financial Sector**, Nigeria has embraced digital technologies for smart banking solutions through Mobile banking apps, online payment platforms, and digital financial services thereby contributing to a more connected and efficient financial ecosystem. Advancements in smart technologies has been witnessed in **Telecommunication Sector** where mobile networks, fiber-optic infrastructure, and smart connectivity solutions continue to contribute to improved communication and connectivity.

In the Energy Sector, energy plays important role for economic development of any country and the effective utilization of energy and usage of cleaner energy resources has become highly significant due to the scarcity of fossil fuel. With the expected growth in world population, the demand for energy has continuously increased and the capability to fulfill future demands of power by grids built many years ago is uncertain, despite the fact that they are regularly upgraded (Mir *et al.*, 2021).

The implementation of smart energy solutions through the use of **Smart Metering** (the concept of IoT, combined with smart metering, which have the potentials to transform residential houses, homes and offices into energy-aware environments (Stojkoska and Trivodaliev, 2017); Energy

Management Systems (EMS) and Smart Lighting (which enables precise control and optimization of energy consumption) all lead to cost savings, energy efficiency, sustainable practices, and the reduction of environmental issues in facility management

A reliable energy source is needed to improve the living standards of people. To achieve this, a new energy infrastructure called the **Smart Grid** is being installed by governments and industries. Smart grid is an energy infrastructure used to better manage the processes of energy generation, transmission, and distribution in an efficient manner (Stojkoska and Trivodaliev, 2017). It integrates ICT with grid power systems to achieve efficient and intelligent energy generation and consumption (Iyer and Agrawal, 2010). It is characterized by a two-way flow of both electricity and information between all stakeholders, thus, providing an effective mechanism for managing the processes, and consumption of energy (Majumder *et al.*, 2017)

Smart technologies continue to evolve, impacting diverse sectors and contributing to the concept of a connected world. From smart grids that optimize energy distribution to IoT-enabled agriculture practices, the environment is sustained and global challenges addressed.

BENEFITS OF SMART TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION

Some of the advantages of the integration of smart technologies in facilities Management include the following:

❖ **Improved Operational Efficiency through Real-time Monitoring**

Smart sensors and devices enable informed decisions to be made promptly by providing real-time data on various aspects of a facility, including energy usage, equipment performance, and environmental conditions, thus saving time and improving operational efficiency.

❖ **Promotion of Sustainability and Energy Efficiency through Predictive Maintenance**

Smart technologies help in identifying potential issues before they escalate, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of assets by allowing for predictive maintenance through continuous monitoring of equipment

❖ **Cost Optimization**

Data analytics and machine learning tools associated with smart technology help facility managers analyze operational data, identify inefficiencies, and implement cost-saving measures more effectively.

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS

Despite the promising benefits, the integration of smart technologies in facility management is not without challenges. Addressing these challenges is crucial for a successful smart technology adoption. There is therefore the need for strategic planning, collaboration, and ongoing evaluation of the integration. Some of these challenges are:

❖ **Data Security Concerns**

The advent of smart technology has brought about increased awareness of cybersecurity and making the security of personal and sensitive data a major concern. In order to continue to maintain User trust, robust cybersecurity measures need to be put in place to mitigate the increasing cyber threats and data breaches.

❖ **Data Privacy and Ethics**

Due to the massive amounts of User data generated by smart devices, privacy compliance, safeguarding sensitive data and ethical use of data is very important in building and maintaining User trust. Therefore, ensuring strong data encryption, database security as

well as secured communication channels is critical for smart technologies (Mir *et al.*, 2021).

❖ **Initial Implementation Cost**

High upfront costs is needed for implementation of smart technologies and their integration in facilities management. There is need to balance investment with the expected Return on Investment (ROI) by considering the long-term benefits against the immediate financial constraints. There are also several costs associated with the usage of these technologies, which include the device cost, operating cost, technological services cost, and maintenance cost amongst others (Majumder *et al.*, 2017). Currently, many IoT products for smart buildings and other industrial applications are expensive and not affordable for most private customers (Mumtaz, *et al.* 2017).

❖ **Complexities of its Integration**

Smart Technologies, for example, the Smart home is a complex system with many discrete devices and systems connected in a common platform. The system needs to be carefully designed to deal with integration issues among different devices and also to have optimum number of sensors in order to avoid redundant data, minimize infrastructure and maintenance cost as well as energy consumption without losing key information (Stojkoska and Trivodaliev, 2017)

❖ **Interoperability Issues**

The incompatibility between different smart devices and systems makes Integration difficulties hinder seamless communication thereby reducing efficiency, increasing costs, and limiting scalability.

❖ **Skill Gaps and Training**

Handling and maintaining smart technologies require specialized skills. Bridging the skill gap among employees can be achieved by investing in training programs and hiring skilled personnel.

❖ **Resistance to Change**

The tendency of employees and stakeholders to resist adopting new technologies cannot be overlooked. This resistance can be overcome by emphasizing benefits and addressing concerns.

❖ **Environmental Impact**

Addressing the environmental impact of smart technology is a global major concern as there is increase in the disposal of outdated smart devices. For sustainability, incorporating eco-friendly practices in technology lifecycles is very crucial.

CONCLUSION

Considering the rapidly evolving nature of technology, the emerging technologies and potential industries trend currently being experienced, the future prospects of smart technologies integration in facility management is very bright. The integration of smart technology in facility management is pivotal for modernizing operations, optimizing resources, and ensuring a safe and efficient environment for the User.

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